

Desigualdades integrales fraccionales y sus q -análogos

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Dedicated to Professor S.L. Kalla

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Resumen

El objeto de este trabajo es establecer algunas desigualdades que envuelven operadores integrales de Saigo. Se usa el cálculo q -fraccional para obtener varios resultados en la teoría de las desigualdades q -integrales. Los resultados dados anteriormente por Purohit y Raina (2013) y Sulaiman (2011) son casos especiales de los obtenidos en este trabajo.

Palabras clave: Desigualdades integrales, operadores integrales fraccionales, operadores q -integrales fraccionales.

On fractional integral inequalities and their q -analogues

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to establish some integral inequalities involving Saigo fractional integral operators. We then use fractional q -calculus for yielding various results in the theory of q -integral inequalities. The results given earlier by Purohit and Raina (2013) and Sulaiman (2011) follow as special cases of our findings.

Key words: Integral inequalities, fractional integral operators, fractional q -integral operators.